

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHIJITH T P bearing USN 6SU21MI001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AISHWARYA RAJENDRAN C V bearing USN 6SU21MI002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKHIL A S bearing USN 6SU21MI003 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKSHITHA SHEKHAWAT bearing USN 6SU21MI004 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSREE P V bearing USN 6SU21MI005 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms APARNA N V bearing USN 6SU21MI006 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARCHANA DIVYAN bearing USN 6SU21MI007 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARSHYA DHANARAJ bearing USN 6SU21MI008 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARUN A bearing USN 6SU21MI009 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms BHAVYA KRISHNA P bearing USN 6SU21MI010 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms C H MUFSINA MUHAMMED RAFI bearing USN 6SU21MI011 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMATH SANA bearing USN 6SU21MI012 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FAYIZ SAKEER HUSSAIN bearing USN 6SU21MI013 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JINTO JOHNY bearing USN 6SU21MI014 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KHADEEJA ZOYA T K bearing USN 6SU21MI015 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUFEEEDA E bearing USN 6SU21MI016 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED ANAS C K bearing USN 6SU21MI017 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIHAL NASHID bearing USN 6SU21MI018 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIKHITHA MANOHAR K bearing USN 6SU21MI019 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RIFANA K M bearing USN 6SU21MI020 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RISWANA K M bearing USN 6SU21MI021 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHIHABUDEEN K S bearing USN 6SU21MI022 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUSMAYA M bearing USN 6SU21MI023 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms V K ANAMIKA bearing USN 6SU21MI024 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ZUHA HUSSAIN bearing USN 6SU21MI025 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146